

A Tale of Two Gammas

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ABSTRACT

In this short paper, I've considered the Gamma constant $\Gamma\{s\}$ and the Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$ as two independent systems. That is, we can not treat $\Gamma(z)$ as the analytic continuation of $\Gamma\{s\}$. It is far more logical to treat them separately.

The Gamma Constant

The integral of the function $f(x) = e^{-x} x^{s-1}$ from 0 to infinity is constant,

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx = \text{constant.}$$

Where s is a complex constant, and denoting the integral by $\Gamma\{s\}$,

$$\Gamma\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx = \text{constant.}$$

$\Gamma\{s\}$ is valid if the real part of the single-valued s is greater than zero,

$$(1) \quad \Gamma\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^s n!}{s(s+1)(s+2)\cdots(s+n)} \quad \Re(s) > 0, s = s.$$

Examples: 1) $\Gamma\{3\} = 2! = 2$. 2) $\Gamma\{4\} = 3! = 6$. 4) $\Gamma\{\frac{1}{2}\} = \sqrt{\pi}$. 5) $\Gamma\{-\frac{1}{2}\} = \text{undefined}$.

While its reflection $\Gamma\{1-s\}$ is valid if the real part of s is less than 1,

$$\Gamma\{1-s\} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^{1-s} n!}{(1-s)(2-s)(3-s)\cdots(n+1-s)} \quad \Re(s) < 1, s = s.$$

Reflection Formula 1

If we multiply $\Gamma\{s\}$ and $\Gamma\{1-s\}$, we obtain the **reflection formula**. It is valid if the real part of s is between 0 and 1,

$$\Gamma\{s\}\Gamma\{1-s\} = \frac{\pi}{\sin\{\pi s\}} \quad 0 < \Re(s) < 1, s = s$$

Examples: 1) $\Gamma\{\frac{1}{2}\}\Gamma\{\frac{1}{2}\} = \pi$. 2) $\Gamma\{-\frac{1}{2}\}\Gamma\{\frac{3}{2}\} = \text{undefined}$. 3) $\Gamma\{\frac{4}{3}\}\Gamma\{-\frac{1}{3}\} = \text{undefined}$.

The Gamma Function

We can deduce from (1) the *existence* of a function $f(z)$. That function is the widely-known Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$. It is known that $\Gamma(z)$ is valid for every z unless z is a negative integer ($z = 0, -1, -2, \dots$)

$$\Gamma(z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^z n!}{z(z+1)(z+2)\cdots(z+n)}.$$

Examples: 1) $\Gamma(3) = 2! = 2$. 2) $\Gamma(4) = 3! = 6$. 4) $\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}) = \sqrt{\pi}$. 5) $\Gamma(-\frac{1}{2}) = -2\sqrt{\pi}$.

$\Gamma\{s\}$ is single-valued while $\Gamma(z)$ has many values (its range). The constant $\Gamma\{s\}$ is just *one* of the values of $\Gamma(z)$, that is

$$\Gamma\{s\} = \Gamma(s).$$

The reflection $\Gamma(1-z)$ is valid for every z except for the positive integers ($z = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

$$\Gamma(1-z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^{1-z} n!}{(1-z)(2-z)(3-z)\cdots(n+1-z)}.$$

Reflection Formula 2

Hence, the reflection formula

$$\Gamma(z)\Gamma(1-z) = \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi z)}$$

is valid for every z except for the integers ($\dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots$).

Examples: 1) $\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}) = \pi$. 2) $\Gamma(-\frac{1}{2})\Gamma(\frac{3}{2}) = -\pi$. 3) $\Gamma(-\frac{1}{3})\Gamma(\frac{4}{3}) \approx -3.6276$.

Two Independent Systems

Thus, we have *two* independent functions,

$$(a) f(x) = e^{-x} x^{s-1} \quad \text{and} \quad (b) f(z) = \Gamma(z).$$

$\Gamma\{s\}$ is single-valued while $\Gamma(z)$ has many values. The single-valued s whose real part *must* be greater than zero for $\Gamma\{s\}$ to exist is simply *one* of the values of z .

$\Gamma(z)$ is *not* the analytic continuation of $\Gamma\{s\}$, but through $\Gamma\{s\}$, we were able to discover the existence of the Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$ and that $\Gamma\{s\}$ is just *one* of the values of $\Gamma(z)$.

The Fallacy of Analytic Continuation

Now, the reason we got $\Gamma(z)$ from $\Gamma\{s\}$ is because of the formula in (1). In its *absence*, it is very difficult or almost impossible to obtain $\Gamma(z)$ from just *one* of its values.

Analytic continuation *implies* that we can obtain the function from just *one* of its values. For example, if $f(2) = 0.5$, then by analytic continuation, we can obtain $f(z)$! These are two of the possible functions:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} \quad \text{and} \quad f(z) = 2.5 - z \quad \text{for} \quad f(2) = 0.5 .$$

This is the reason why analytic continuation *is* faulty. Because to obtain the function from its values, such samples must be sufficiently large. One sample won't do it.

Therefore, analytic continuation taken to its ultimate logic is absurd.